

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

Document info

Title	Report on current practices for Training Coordinators and TrP Node members (in relation to activities and onboarding), highlight areas for recognition, and redefine the existing onboarding process
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ELIXIR Abbreviations and Acronyms

TrP	Training Platform
TrC(s)	Training Coordinator(s)
ExCo	Executive Committee
CoS	Commissioned Service
F2F	Face to face
HoN(s)	Head of Node(s)
AHM	All Hands Meeting
NC(s)	Node Coordinator(s)
TeC(s)	Technical Coordinator(s)
TrCG	Training Coordinators Group
TeCG	Technical Coordinators Group
FG(s)	Focus Group(s)
TMD	Training Metric Database
TtT	Train-the-Trainer
WP(s)	Work package(s)
WG(s)	Working Group(s)

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Executive Summary

The Milestone M3.10 “Report on current practices for Training Coordinators and TrP Node members (in relation to activities and onboarding), highlight areas for recognition, and redefine the existing onboarding process” is focused on identifying the roles and responsibilities of TrCs but also to indicate the existing activities of TrP Node members. This was achieved, based on the M3.9 collected critical components of the TrP. In this Milestone, a comprehensive documentation has been collected from past ELIXIR meetings (monthly, F2F, All Hands, related workshops) and related documentation (public and private, eg. Elixir site, papers, posters, Handbooks, deliverables, intranet etc) in order to identify current practices.

The milestone M3.10¹ covers the current roles and responsibilities for TrCs based on the Node and ELIXIR Europe point of view. All that information was collected from dedicated meetings and documented in a Miro Board². Also the report presents current practices for TrP members. The existing onboarding **document**³ has been updated. All those documents have been read, commented and approved from all TrCs other WPs, related Commission Services (STEERS, PeoplePulse) and will be enriched from all those ongoing programs.

Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone

The process of this milestone has been in close link to the ELIXIR-STEERS WP₄ and also with the PeoplePulse program. Great communication and collaboration with knowledge exchange from different perspectives have been achieved. While there are many differences between TrCs roles and responsibilities across ELIXIR Nodes, this also sets a challenge to implement the same practices for the Node Training strategies. TrCs and TrP Node members must be engaged in order to achieve recognition from activities and this milestone will help identify those activities.

From this Milestone, another critical outcome is the importance of the TrP Liaison. The commitment of the Liaison and the flow of communication, and collaborations and cooperation between ELIXIR entities is also a challenge since Training is related to all ELIXIR components.

Documenting and revising the current practices for TrCs have also helped identify new critical components^{2,4}. The report on the Critical Components of the TrP (M3.9) is a work in progress and will be finalized during 2025, taking into account also the important challenges reported⁵. ELIXIR Europe has evolved over the years to meet the needs of existing and new Nodes and the community; in order to achieve this, TrP and the TrCs must adapt to new challenges.

¹ [WP3 Milestone 3.10 Current Practices](#) (ELIXIR Training Platform)

² Continuation of TrCG Miro Board - 2024 <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVK3LnuuY=>

³ [Training Platform - Onboarding info](#)

⁴ [M3.9 ELIXIR Milestone Report.docx](#) (ELIXIR Training Platform)

⁵ TrCG Miro Board - 2024 <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVNP0h9mw=>